

AGEMERA

Critical Raw Materials for
a Resilient Europe

ETHICS REPORT 1

Deliverable 7.5

This project has received funding under the European Union's Horizon Europe
research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101058178.

Project no. 101058178
Project acronym: AGEMERA
Project title: Agile Exploration and Geo-Modelling for European Critical Raw Materials
Call: HORIZON-CL4-2021-RESILIENCE-01
Start date of project: 01.08.2022
Duration: 36 months
Deliverable title: D7.5 ETHICS REPORT 1
Due date of deliverable: 31.1.2024
Actual date of submission: 31.1.2024
Deliverable Lead Partner: University of Oulu
Dissemination level: Public

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Document History

Version	Date	Note	Revised by
01	18.1.2024	Draft version	E-RN
02	28.1.2024	Draft for commenting	E-RN, JJ
03	31.1.2024	Final version	E-RN

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Executive Summary

Ethics Report 1

During the first reporting period of the Agile Exploration and Geo-Modelling for European Critical Raw Materials (AGEMERA) project, the research ethics monitoring plan was created and delivered.

Guidelines for good research and publishing practises were given and a procedure for dealing with possible notices of violations of research integrity, research misconduct or other unacceptable practices was created and accepted.

The Ethics Advisor gave presentations and conducted a workshop on research ethics and research integrity. Also, other presentations and workshops were organized to remind the importance of acceptable practices and to widen the knowledge on these issues.

During the first reporting period, there has not been any need to activate the AGEMERA procedure to deal with violations of research integrity, research misconduct or other unacceptable practices.

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List of Acronyms

AGEMERA	Agile Exploration and Geo-Modelling for European Critical Raw Materials
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CRM	Critical Raw Material
D	Deliverable
DMP	Data Management Plan
GA	Grant Agreement
SPSS	Statistical Package for the Social Sciences
TENK	Finnish National Board on Research Integrity
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

The research ethics guidelines for the AGEMERA project are based on the [European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity](#). According to which, good research practices are based on fundamental principles of research integrity. These principles are reliability, honesty, respect and accountability. The principles and practices of research ethics monitoring in the AGEMERA project are described in the Research Ethics Monitoring Plan (deliverable 7.2).

Professor Riitta Keiski from the University of Oulu, Faculty of Technology, Environmental and Chemical Engineering Research unit was nominated as the research ethics advisor for the AGEMERA project. Prof. Keiski has long academic experience and is known for her ethics-related duties. She has been e.g. a member in the Finnish National Board on Research Integrity (TENK) since 2007, vice-chair (2007-2010) and chair since 2019.

In this report research ethics monitoring actions during the first period (M1-M18) are described, as well as, the guidance material and workshops. The document also includes a report about data protection concerning activities that involve local public and stakeholders in WP2 and WP5. In the third chapter possible violations of research integrity, research misconduct and other unacceptable practices are described.

2 Research ethics monitoring

2.1 Actions during the first reporting period

Research Ethics Advisor prof. Riitta Keiski introduced herself to the AGEMERA consortium in the kick-off meeting in October 2022 giving a presentation.

Preparing the research ethics monitoring plan included workshops and collaboration between the ethics advisor and coordinator, as well as discussions in the WP 7 team meeting and WP Managers' meeting. Feedback from WP7 team members was received to develop the draft. The research ethics monitoring plan (Deliverable 7.2) was submitted as planned.

Research ethics guidelines for the AGEMERA project are included in the research ethics monitoring plan. There were presentations on these guidelines and information about the research ethics monitoring in the project's general assembly meeting in May 2023 and in October 2023.

Online workshop on research ethics was organized in October 2023. The feedback showed it very useful.

Research ethics and data management issues have been combined in forms of questionnaires and other tasks. As part of the WP4 tasks, data inventory and AI platform user list has been created. Data inventory table includes data sources, EOD georeferenced products and non-georeferenced products. AGEMERA AI platform user list is also in the project's online workspace.

Collaboration between tasks in various ways have been done to have the research ethics issues as an ordinary part of the project implementation. Internal communication team meeting in October 2023 included publishing and authorship topics. Adjunct professor Ossi Kotavaara gave a presentation about the Vancouver Protocol and recommendations for authorship.

Intellectual property rights (IPR) and IPR management as part of the WP 6 tasks comes close to the research ethics issues. IPR workshop was organized online in November 2023. It included the basics of IPR and freedom to operate. During the first reporting period special workshops for copyright issues and patenting were planned. These workshops will be organized in 2024.

During the first reporting period the Project Leader and the Project Manager have had meeting with the Research Ethics Advisor and Innovation Manager when needed.

2.2 Guidance material and workshops

Guidelines for research ethics in the AGEMERA can be summarised as follows:

The AGEMERA project will be carried out in line with the highest ethical standards and the applicable EU, international and national law on ethical principles. All violations of research integrity, research misconduct and other unacceptable practices are taken seriously in the AGEMERA project.

The research ethics guidelines for the AGEMERA project are based on the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity. According to which, good research practices are based on fundamental principles of research integrity. These principles are:

- Reliability in ensuring the quality of research, reflected in the design, the methodology, the analysis and the use of resources.
- Honesty in developing, undertaking, reviewing, reporting and communicating research in a transparent, fair, full and unbiased way.
- Respect for colleagues, research participants, society, ecosystems, cultural heritage and the environment.
- Accountability for the research from idea to publication, for its management and organisation, for training, supervision and mentoring, and for its wider impacts.

All violations of research integrity, research misconduct and other unacceptable practices are taken seriously in the AGEMERA project.

It is in the interest of the AGEMERA consortium, that any violations are handled in a consistent and transparent fashion. That is why the AGEMERA procedure in case of violations of research integrity, research misconduct and other unacceptable practices has been communicated in various team meetings and General Assembly meetings.

Steps of the procedure:

1. In case of noticing or doubting any of the actions mentioned in the plan, the matter should be brought up and discussed confidentially with the Coordinator and the Ethical Advisor.
2. After the discussion, all parties involved will be contacted and heard in fairness to all parties.
3. After getting the whole picture, measures and procedures are decided and conducted confidentially in order to protect those involved. Anyone accused of research misconduct is presumed innocent until proven otherwise.
4. Appropriate restorative actions will be taken, if needed, to ensure fulfilling the goals of the AGEMERA project.

The AGEMERA – Research Ethics and Integrity Monitoring Plan and Guidance workshop in October 2023 included following topics:

- AGEMERA project – research ethics monitoring plan

- Ethics instructions for researchers during the project planning and running periods
- The Finnish Code of Conduct for Research Integrity
- Research integrity adviser system in Finland
- Authorship and research integrity
- Ethical principles of research with human participants
- Ethics related to research focus on the environment and nature
- Ethics of artificial intelligence
- The European code of conduct for research integrity
- The key guidelines and publications by TENK

The material of the workshop is in the project's online workspace for all team members to use. Also the materials of the IPR workshop (11/2023) and publishing recommendations/ Vancouver Protocol presented in the internal communication team meeting (10/2023) are openly available for AGEMERA team members, as well as all the meeting minutes.

2.3 Data protection concerning activities that involve local public and stakeholders in WP 2 and WP 5

Data management plan (deliverable 7.3) was created for the AGEMERA project, that implements a combination of multisource geoscientific data and data fusion and processing powered by data analytics, data fusion and machine-learning algorithms. The data is collected and gathered into the AGEMERA platform, which combines the public, e.g., earth observation data, project-wise collected new geoscientific field data, drone, muographic and ambient seismic tomography data and converts the information into actionable intelligence for mineral potential and mineral exploration data. The project surveys local communities' concerns and hopes regarding mineral exploration and compiles the generalised and anonymised results into an open-access database.

The data management report (deliverable 7.4) describes more closely the actions taken during the first reporting period.

According to the accepted plan the ethics report must include a report about data protection concerning activities that involve local public and stakeholders in WP2 and WP5.

The WP 2 (Impact of CRM on Green and Digital Transition) includes tasks 2.1. Development of SoftGIS-based approach and questionnaires to assess local acceptance and sustainability, 2.2: Small group interviews, 2.3: Launch of university courses, and 2.4: Organisation of public awareness events.

During the first reporting period, for the task 2.1 data was gathered by web-based questionnaire (n_193) about local people's perceptions on mineral exploration and mining (n = 293). The format of this final, sensitive data is SPSS and maps. This data is stored locally by the responsible partner, University of Lapland. The data does not include any names. The results are reported based on the postal codes. In case just a few answers were received from a certain area, the answers are included in a larger area to protect privacy of individuals.

In this context, generalisation means that the results of the questionnaires and surveys are topically categorised under top-level terms. This also helps to anonymise the data. Depending on the number of respondents per designated area, neighbouring areas have been included to have a large enough population to increase the level of anonymity within the data. As the number of respondents was sizable, but per region, it is not enough to form any form of statistical generalisation of the people's perception on mineral exploration and mining, but it is a collection of people's opinions.

For the task 2.3 written answers from students were collected by webropol survey during the first reporting period. The sensitive final data is stored by the responsible partner, University of Lapland.

The WP 5 (Dissemination, Communication and Collaboration) consists of tasks 5.1. Dissemination, communication plan and visual identity, 5.2. Joint dissemination actions and scientific outreach, 5.3. Communication and public outreach, and 5.4. Collaboration and synergies.

AGEMERA Newsletter serves the goals of the tasks 5.2, 5.3 and 5.4. The data set of newsletter subscribers include email addresses of local public and shareholders's representatives. The data format is a SQL database. The sensitive final data include recipient's first name, last name and email address. The data set is stored locally by the responsible partner, Geonardo Environmental Technologies Ltd.

For the task 5.1 visual identity (logos, templates) for the AGEMERA project has been created. The files, that are essential for project documentation, communication and collaboration, do not include any data that involve local public and stakeholders. These files are stored in the intraproject repository,

2.4 Monitoring

Ethical issues and the planned activities in the research ethics monitoring plan have been followed in the WP Manager meetings as part of the WP 7 status report and in the WP 7 team meetings. The status report has been given in the General Assembly meetings, too.

The Ethics Advisor has worked closely with the consortium being available, conducting the workshop and taking part in General Assembly meetings.

As part of the risk assessment, the research ethics was also evaluated as the state of play of the foreseen critical risks and mitigation actions was given for the first reporting period.

3 Possible notices of violations of research integrity, research misconduct or other unacceptable practices

During the first reporting period, there has not been any need to activate the AGEMERA procedure to deal with violations of research integrity, research misconduct or other unacceptable practices. There has not been any notification nor doubt reported to the Coordinator.

It is in the interest of the AGEMERA consortium, that any violations are handled in a consistent and transparent fashion. That is why the research ethics issues and research ethics monitoring plan will be regularly reviewed during the next reporting period, too.

